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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF ORAL SECNIDAZOLE AND
CLINDAMYCIN IN TREATMENT OF BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS**¹Dr. Maida Khan, ²Dr Hafiz Hasan Fazal Sheikh, ³Dr. Sana Khalid¹Mayo Hospital Lahore²Medical Officer, DHQ Hospital Hafizabad³Combined Military Hospital Sialkot**Abstract:**

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy of using secnidazole as single per oral dose in comparison with clindamycin for treating bacterial vaginosis.

Method: The study design followed in this research was double blind randomized controlled trial. It was conducted at Shifa foundation, Community Health Centre over period of 2 years and 11 months from March 2012 to February 2015. Informed consent was taken from all cases and diagnosis was confirmed by physical examination and presence of milky discharge was confirmed, followed by confirmation on microscopy by looking for clue cells and positive amine test. Exclusion criteria was pregnancy, immunocompromised state or diabetic women. Doctor, patient and pharmacist blinding was ensured. Sample was divided into two groups, group 1 was given pack 1 medicine containing clindamycin and oral placebo while group 2 was given pack 2 which had 2g secnidazole in it along with placebo topical vaginal preparation. Recovery criteria was reversal of two out of following three symptoms i.e. milky vaginal discharge, negative amine test, normal Nugent score after 15 days of treatment initiation.

Results: 96% cases who were on clindamycin treatment recovered on 15th day while only 23% patients recovered by taking secnidazole orally.

Key Words: vaginal clindamycin, bacterial vaginosis, oral secnidazole, treatment.

Corresponding author:**Maida Khan,**

Mayo Hospital, Lahore.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

A polymicrobial vaginal infection which leads to change in normal vaginal flora. Normal commensals in vagina are lactobacilli such as *L crispatus* which keeps the vaginal pH in acidic range by secreting lactic acid and hence prevent from vaginal infections. The culprit organisms for bacterial vaginosis include *G vaginalis*, *Prevotella*, *Bacteroides*, *Mobiluncus*, *ureaplasma* and *Mycoplasma*¹. The complications associated with bacterial vaginosis include reduced fertility rate, PID (Pelvic inflammatory disease), Preterm labor, premature placental membranes rupture¹. ⁴It is one of the commonest STD (sexually transmitted disease).

²Bacterial vaginosis is highly prevalent disease amongst pregnant women. ³Amsel criteria is used for its diagnosis; pH less than five, milky white discharge, amine order after mixing with base, clue cells on gram staining. 3 out of 4 positive points confirm presence of disease. The clue cells make the most reliable diagnostic marker with sensitivity and specificity of 93% and 70%, respectively.

⁵Metronidazole is commonly used for treating bacterial vaginosis and its effectiveness has already been approved. The clindamycin as effective treatment against bacterial vaginosis is in use across the globe. Its route of administration doesn't change the effectivity in significant range. Secnidazole 2grams orally in a single dose has been tested and approved as effective treatment against bacterial vaginosis amongst asymptomatic patients and uncomplicated cases. Clindamycin is a better treatment option for *A vaginae*, *G vaginalis*, *M spp*. However, *Prevotella*, *Peptinophilus*, *Bacteroides spp*. Shows positive response to metronidazole as compared to clindamycin⁶. This research aims at studying the effect of secnidazole in symptomatic patients with bacterial vaginosis.

METHODOLOGY:

The study design followed in this research was double blind randomized controlled trial. It was conducted at Shifa foundation, Community Health Centre over period of 2 years and 11 months from March 2012 to February 2015. No ethical issue certificate was taken for ethical committee. Informed consent was taken from all cases. Patients presented with complaint of milky vaginal discharge were enrolled in study and were examined and investigated for the confirmation of diagnosis. Pelvic examination

was done and secretions were collected after speculum examination, then microscopy was performed. Those patients with vaginal pH more than 4 and clue cells on microscopy were enrolled in study and labelled confirmed case. Exclusion criteria was pregnancy, immunocompromised or diabetic females.

The patients were divided into group 1 and 2 and medicines were divided into two packets, each pack was labelled as 1 or 2 with different packet content. Blinding of physician, patient and pharmacist was done about medicine packet content. Packet 1 had clindamycin and oral placebo in it while while 2 grams secnidazole along with placebo vaginal cream was present in the other packet. Packet 1 was given to group 1 while packet 2 was given to group 2. All patients were re-evaluated after 15 days.

SPPS 21 was brought in use to analyse data. Percentages and frequencies were used to present qualitative data. McNemar's test was used to compare the outcome. P value <0.05 was considered significant. Despite of telephonic contact with the patients, ten patients were lost to follow up.

RESULTS:

192 patients were enrolled and were divided into group 1 and 2 randomly. Both groups were given respective medicine packets. 182 patients out of the total sample remained till the 15th day follow-up, rest of them were lost to follow-up despite of repeated telephonic contact. Each group contained 91 patients and were given clindamycin and secnidazole, respectively. Pelvic examination of all cases was done. 74 patients i.e. 81% showed positive amine test in group 1, while 82 patients i.e. 90% were positive in secnidazole group. Clue cells were positive in 91% and 92% in both groups respectively as shown in table-1.

The statistics of 15th day follow up in both groups were as follow. In group 1, who received clindamycin and placebo oral 84 patients (92%) were discharge free, 87 (96%) patients had negative clue cells and amine test. Statistics of secnidazole receiving group were 15 (16%) patients were discharge free, 63 (69%) patients were still amine test positive, clue cells were detected in 77% i.e. 70 patients, respectively which shows failure to treatment with secnidazole in group 2 as compared to clindamycin in group 1 as shown in table-1.

Table-1: Amsel criteria before and after treatment.

parameters	Before clindamycin	After 15 days of clindamycin	Before secnidazole	After 15 days of secnidazole
Clue cells	83 (91%)	4 (4%)	84 (92%)	70 (77%)
Vaginal discharge	91 (100%)	7 (8%)	91 (100%)	76 (84%)
Amine test	74 (81%)	4 (4%)	82 (90%)	63 (69%)
p-value	Less than 0.0001		Less than 0.0001	

Thus there was statistically significant difference in both groups and clindamycin was found to be a better treatment option for bacterial vaginosis in comparison with secnidazole.

DISCUSSION:

^{6,7,8}Multiple drugs have been tested so far to treat the bacterial vaginosis. The most commonly used drugs are clindamycin in either topical or systemic form but the route of administration doesn't affect the drug efficacy in treating BV. Secnidazole, like metronidazole has been tested and its use for treating asymptomatic BV or complication free disease has been approved. 2 gram single dose secnidazole and 2% clindamycin was given to patients by randomly allocating into two groups. The double blind randomized controlled trial was conducted in this regard.

Similar researches have been done by many other authors too. But due to less data available in Pakistani population the researchers aim to study its role by targeting local Pakistani population.

⁹Karthick A has studied the use of sustained release secnidazole gels for curing BV. While the drug safety and major side effects associated with secnidazole treatment were studied by ¹⁰Darpo B, et al. and concluded the least cardiac side effects of under study drug.

⁷Nyirjesy P, et al. conducted a study which was published in 2018. In his research he concluded the effective use of secnidazole for treating the BV and also he studied and approved its use in preventing serious complications. In already complicated BV patients the secnidazole benefits are not statistically significant. However, more research work is needed to bring the use of secnidazole into a better conclusion, so that STDs can be effectively and timely controlled by using multiple regimens.

CONCLUSION:

The effect of clindamycin in treating bacterial vaginosis is better than single dose oral secnidazole.

REFERENCES:

- 1- Paladine, Heather L, Desai, Urmi A. Vaginitis: diagnosis and treatment. *American family Physician* 2018; 97(5): 321-29.
- 2- Sabour S, Arzanlou M, Vaez H, Rahimi G,

Sahebkar A, Khademi F, et al. Prevalence of bacterial vaginosis in pregnant and non-pregnant Iranian women: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Archives of Gynecology and Obstetrics* 2018.

- 3- Reid G. Is bacterial vaginosis a disease? *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2018; 102(2): 553-58.
- 4- Dirani G, Zannoli S, Pedna MF, congestri F, Farabegoli P, Dalmo B, et al. Bacterial vaginosis: epidemiological, clinical and diagnostic updates 2017; 32(4).
- 5- Ghosh AP, Aycock C, Schwebke JR. Susceptibility of clinical isolates of *Trichomonas vaginalis* to metronidazole and secnidazole- an in vitro study. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 2018; 16(3).
- 6- Chavoustie SE, Gertsten JK, Samuel MJ, Schwebke JR. a phase 3, multicentre, prospective, open label study to evaluate the safety of a single dose of secnidazole 2 gram for the treatment of women and postmenarchal adolescent with bacterial vaginosis. *Journal of Women's Health* 2018.
- 7- Nyirjesy P, Schwebke JR. Secnidazole: next generation antimicrobial agent for bacterial vaginosis treatment. *Future medicine* 2018.
- 8- Passos MRL. Vulvovaginitis. *Atlas of Sexually Transmitted Diseases* 2018: 203-237.
- 9- Karthick A, Devi R, Hari V. Investigation of sustained release mucoadhesive *In-situ* gel system of secnidazole for the persistent treatment of vaginal infection. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology* 2018; 43: 362-68.
- 10- Darpo B, Xue H, Adetoro N, Matthews BG, pentikis NS. Thorough QT/QTc evaluation of the cardiac safety of secnidazole at therapeutic and supratherapeutic doses in healthy individuals. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology* 2018; 58(3): 286-93.